

Paediatric *Tui Na* for Childhood Nocturnal Enuresis: A Review of Theoretical Foundations and Clinical Application.

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Abstract

Childhood nocturnal enuresis (CNE), defined as involuntary urination during sleep in children over five years of age, is a prevalent condition that can significantly affect emotional well-being, family dynamics, and quality of life. Despite numerous available treatments, both behavioural and pharmacological, many cases remain refractory or prone to relapse. Within Traditional Chinese Medicine (TCM), Paediatric *Tui Na* is a therapeutic massage designed for children. It has been described as an effective non-invasive intervention aimed at restoring energetic balance and regulating organ function.

Evidence indicates that paediatric *Tui Na* can significantly reduce the frequency of enuretic episodes by promoting the energetic regulation of the Kidney, Spleen, and Bladder systems, enhancing urinary control, and improving sleep quality. In addition to physiological regulation, improvements in emotional security and self-esteem have been consistently reported. The therapy's safety profile and its acceptance among children further support its clinical use.

Paediatric *Tui Na* represents a promising, safe, and integrative therapeutic approach for childhood nocturnal enuresis. Its combination of physiological and psychological benefits makes it a valuable adjunct or alternative to conventional treatments. Further controlled clinical studies are necessary to consolidate its evidence base and expand its integration into multidisciplinary paediatric care.

This narrative review aims to analyse the theoretical foundations, mechanisms of action, and clinical evidence supporting the use of Paediatric *Tui Na* in the treatment of childhood nocturnal enuresis.

Keywords: Childhood Nocturnal Enuresis; Paediatric *Tui Na*; Traditional Chinese Medicine; Chinese Paediatrics.

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1. Introduction

CNE is characterised by the involuntary loss of urine in children from the age of five, a stage in which urinary control should already be established, occurring at least twice a week¹. According to the American Psychiatric Association, nocturnal enuresis is considered when a child urinates in bed at least twice a month. The ICD-10 (International Classification of Diseases, 10th version), on the other hand, defines the condition as the loss of urine at least once a month, for three consecutive months². In the first months of life, urination is reflexive and involuntary. Around the age of one, there is an increase in bladder capacity and neural maturation of the frontal and parietal regions, which allows the child to recognise the sensation of a full bladder, although still without control over the act of urinating^{3,4}. Voluntary control of urination, mediated by the cerebral cortex, is acquired later, allowing control according to social norms⁵. Daytime urinary control is usually consolidated by the age of three and nocturnal control between four and five years. The absence of this control after this age characterises CNE⁶. The disorder is common in

childhood, with a similar prevalence worldwide, affecting approximately 30% of children at 4 years, 10% at 7 years, 3% at 12 years, and 1% at 18 years, being more frequent in boys and with a family history of enuresis ^{7,8}. It is a transient condition, with a tendency for spontaneous resolution in about 15% of cases per year ⁹.

Enuresis can be classified as:

- Primary: When the child has never acquired urinary control and has no organic alterations, such as urinary tract infection, neurological dysfunction, or urological disorders.
- Secondary: Occurs after a minimum period of six months of continence and is frequently associated with emotional factors or stressful situations, such as parental separation, a change of school, or the birth of a sibling ¹⁰.
- Monosymptomatic: When the only symptom is nocturnal urine loss.
- Polysymptomatic (or complex): When it is associated with other urinary symptoms, such as urinary urgency, daytime incontinence, a weak stream, dysuria (painful urination), or pollakiuria (increased urinary frequency with decreased urinary volume) ¹¹⁻¹⁴.

Enuresis is a multifactorial disorder, involving physical, genetic, psychological, and social aspects ^{10,15}. Although some studies indicate that emotional and family factors are not the direct cause of enuresis, with psychological symptoms being a consequence of the problem ^{13,16}, other authors reinforce the association of the cause of enuresis with pre-existing behavioural or psychological disorders ^{10,11,14}.

In allopathic medicine, treatment involves behavioural and pharmacological approaches. Behavioural measures include controlling fluid intake, urinating before sleep, and treating constipation, if present. As a pharmacological approach, the use of desmopressin and imipramine can reduce nocturnal enuretic episodes, but with limitations and adverse effects ¹⁷⁻¹⁹. In addition to these approaches, the use of a nocturnal alarm is considered the most effective long-term method in cases that do not have organic causes, promoting the learning of waking up to urinate ²⁰⁻²².

In TCM, nocturnal enuresis is also defined as the involuntary loss of urine during sleep in children over five years of age, and for some authors, from three years onwards ^{23,24}. The formation and excretion of urine are related to the proper functioning of body fluid metabolism (*Jin Ye*), which depends on the harmony and proper functioning of the Kidney, Lung, and Spleen systems. From the perspective of Traditional Chinese Medicine, Nocturnal Enuresis is understood as the result of a congenital deficiency of Kidney *Qi*, a deficiency of Lung and Spleen *Qi*, or the accumulation of dampness-heat in the Liver meridian, factors that compromise the Bladder's function in controlling urination ²⁴⁻²⁷. In addition to the main patterns, the residual pathogenic factor is also considered, which may be associated with various causes, such as recurrent infections not completely resolved, inappropriate use of medications, and the administration of vaccines, as these factors can also interfere with water metabolism ²⁸. The emotional factor is also recognised as a possible cause of enuresis. During phases of childhood life in which significant changes in routine occur, such as entering a new school, parental separation, the birth of a sibling, the loss of a loved one or pet, states of mental agitation may arise. This condition favours an increase in the physiological heat of the Heart, which, in turn, consumes Kidney *Qi*. When the Kidney is weakened, its function of controlling the sphincters is compromised, resulting in the occurrence of enuresis ²⁹.

TCM distinguishes different *syndrome patterns* (energetic diagnoses) associated with CNE, according to the following signs and symptoms ^{24-27,29-31}:

1. Kidney *Qi* deficiency, characterised by weakness, cold limbs, and abundant clear urine;
2. Spleen and Lung *Qi* deficiency, often linked to fatigue, poor appetite, and loose stools and;
3. Damp-heat accumulation in the Liver meridian, manifesting as irritability, thirst, and scanty yellow urine.

While Western medicine primarily employs behavioural interventions, enuresis alarms, and pharmacotherapy (such as desmopressin and imipramine) to manage CNE, these treatments can be associated with side effects and relapse upon discontinuation^{5,13,14,17,18,23}. In contrast, TCM emphasises restoring systemic balance and addressing the root cause of the dysfunction, often integrating acupuncture, herbal medicine, moxibustion, auriculotherapy, cupping, dietary therapy, and *Tui Na*, as non-invasive, holistic interventions^{25,32,33}.

Among these, *Pediatric Tui Na* is a specialised form of Chinese therapeutic massage for children. It has gained attention for its safety, accessibility, and effectiveness³⁴⁻³⁶. By applying gentle manipulations on specific meridians and acupoints, *Tui Na* aims to harmonise *Qi* and blood (*Xue*), strengthen organ function, and promote the child's physical and emotional equilibrium. Clinical observations and controlled trials suggest that *Pediatric Tui Na* can significantly reduce the frequency of enuretic episodes, improve bladder control, and enhance sleep and emotional stability²³.

Given the increasing interest in integrative paediatric care, this review seeks to synthesise theoretical foundations and available evidence regarding the application of paediatric *Tui Na* in the treatment of childhood nocturnal enuresis. Through a narrative synthesis of classical literature and modern research, this paper aims to contextualise the role of *Tui Na* within both traditional Chinese medical theory and contemporary clinical practice.

2. Methodology

The research was carried out by analysing various sources, including specialised books on Traditional Chinese Medicine, scientific articles focused on child health, and publications available in academic databases such as SciELO, Google Scholar, PubMed, and CNKI. The following keywords were used for the search and selection of materials: *Childhood Nocturnal Enuresis*, *Traditional Chinese Medicine*, *Chinese paediatrics*, and *paediatric Tui Na*. Through this review, the intention is to deepen the understanding of the foundations and therapeutic benefits of *Tui Na* in the management of Childhood Nocturnal Enuresis, as well as to highlight the relevance of its integration with other therapeutic approaches. In this way, the study seeks to contribute to the promotion of children's health and well-being in a comprehensive and effective manner.

3. Results and Discussion

3.1. Pathophysiology of Childhood Nocturnal Enuresis from the Perspective of Conventional Medicine

CNE is a multifactorial disorder characterised by involuntary urination during sleep after the age when bladder control should normally be established. Its aetiology is complex, involving an interaction of genetic, physiological, psychological, and environmental factors^{5,9-15}. Studies suggest that delayed neurological maturation, altered circadian rhythm of antidiuretic hormone (ADH) secretion, reduced bladder capacity, and sleep arousal difficulties contribute significantly to its occurrence³⁷⁻⁴¹.

Studies indicate that most children with nocturnal enuresis have the primary and monosymptomatic type, meaning they have never acquired nocturnal urinary control and do not present other associated symptoms. A large part of these cases is related to inadequate training of urination habits, especially during the potty-training process and in controlling fluid intake.¹⁰ To a lesser extent, there are organic causes involved, more frequent

in the secondary and polysymptomatic forms, such as urological malformations, inflammation, urinary tract infection, constipation that puts pressure on the bladder, diabetes, kidney failure, and neurological and sleep disorders ²⁸.

Genetic factors play a relevant role; if one of the parents had a history of enuresis, the risk in the child is about 30%, and if both had the disorder in childhood, the possibility of the child developing it can exceed 70% ⁴²⁻⁴⁶.

Although emotional factors are not always the primary cause, they can exacerbate or perpetuate enuresis by influencing sleep patterns and arousal thresholds ⁴⁷⁻⁴⁹. Current conventional treatments include behavioural interventions, such as fluid restriction before sleep, scheduled voiding, and the use of nocturnal alarms, as well as pharmacological therapies, mainly desmopressin and imipramine. While these approaches can be effective, relapse after treatment discontinuation is frequent, and adverse effects are not uncommon ^{5,13,14,17,18,23}.

These limitations have encouraged the exploration of integrative and complementary therapies, particularly those emphasising non-invasive and holistic approaches, such as those found in TCM.

3.2. Childhood Nocturnal Enuresis According to Traditional Chinese Medicine

From the TCM perspective, urinary control depends on the proper regulation of *Qi*, *Yin-Yang* balance, and the harmonious functioning of the Kidney, Spleen, Lung, and Liver systems ^{24-27,29}. When these systems become imbalanced, water metabolism is disturbed, leading to the involuntary release of urine during sleep.

TCM classifies CNE primarily into three syndrome patterns (*zheng*):

Kidney *Qi* Deficiency

This is the most frequent pattern in CNE. The Kidney governs growth, bone development, and reproductive functions; in children, much of its energy is directed toward growth, making it prone to deficiency. When Kidney *Qi* is insufficient, the Bladder loses its ability to consolidate urine, resulting in frequent or abundant urination at night ^{24,29,50}. Clinical features include pale complexion, cold limbs, clear urine, and a deep, slow pulse. Emotional instability, especially fear and insecurity, may further weaken the Kidney's control function ^{28,29}.

Constitutional alterations of the Kidney may be present from birth, leading to subsequent deficiency of its *Qi* ^{24,29}. Kidney *Qi* deficiency is considered the primary cause of most CNE cases. This occurs because the Kidney is responsible for bone growth, marrow formation, and brain development, directing a large part of its energy toward the child's growth and maturation. This constant overload can result in energetic deficiency of the Kidney. With the onset of puberty, when growth becomes regulated mainly by hormones, a tendency toward remission of Enuresis is observed. This phenomenon is related to the physiological increase in Kidney *Yang*, characteristic of adolescence ³⁰. Children who present this syndrome generally have a weak constitution, generalised energetic deficiency, low vitality, slow digestion and growth, and greater susceptibility to colds ²⁶. They are frequently described as quiet, shy, distracted, with a tendency toward overweight, and sensitive to cold. From a clinical point of view, they present manifestations such as clear and abundant urine during the day, pale tongue with thin white coating, and deep, thin, or slow pulse, typical signs of a cold deficiency-type syndrome. In more severe cases, cold limbs and intellectual deficit may occur, as Kidney deficiency leads to insufficient marrow production and brain malnutrition, which may be associated with cognitive deficits. In certain cases, Kidney *Qi* deficiency can evolve into Kidney *Yang* deficiency, intensifying the enuresis condition. In this condition, *Yang* becomes unable to warm and sustain bodily functions, resulting in pallor, aversion to cold, and cold extremities, representing more severe stages of the syndrome. What characterises this pattern distinctively is the elimination of a large volume of urine during sleep. Kidney *Qi* deficiency compromises the

Bladder's control function, resulting in failure in water metabolism. This dysfunction explains both the act of urinating involuntarily at night and the increase in daytime urinary volume^{24,25,50}. The Fire of Ming Men, considered the Original Fire and the vital flame of the organism, constitutes the basis of body heat and is intimately related to Kidney *Yang*. When this Fire weakens, physiological functions become slow, leading to a lack of vital impulse, developmental delay, and inability to contain urine effectively. Furthermore, children present a physiological Heart heat, which can consume Kidney *Yang*. This energetic deficiency prevents the Kidney from adequately controlling the sphincters, favouring the occurrence of enuresis. As Kidney *Yang* is consumed, there is a predominance of *Yin*, characterised by excess fluids, cold, and downward movement of energy, resulting in involuntary urinary elimination²⁹. Children with this pattern also tend to present insecurity and recurrent fears, factors that may derive both from their constitutional nature and from external influences, such as family, school, or social environment^{28,29}. The immature Shen contributes to alterations of the *Zhi*, the mental and emotional aspect of the Kidney, associated with courage and fear. Situations of emotional instability, especially frequent fear and stress, weaken Kidney *Qi*, compromising urinary control²⁹.

Spleen and Lung *Qi* Deficiency

The Spleen governs transformation and transportation of fluids, while the Lung regulates water pathways through dispersing and descending functions. Recurrent respiratory illnesses, poor diet, or medication misuse can weaken these organs, impairing their fluid metabolism and leading to enuresis^{24,28,50}. Symptoms include fatigue, poor appetite, loose stools, spontaneous sweating, and weak voice. Since the Spleen governs the muscles, its deficiency may reduce sphincter tone, exacerbating urinary. Due to the action of pathogenic factors, each episode of respiratory disturbance alters the metabolism of body fluids, compromising the functions of the Lung and Spleen. In these cases, enuresis tends to be temporary and generally disappears spontaneously after the resolution of the illness. However, there are situations in which the child presents chronic weakness of the Lung, Spleen, and Ming Men, associated with a history of recurrent digestive and respiratory disturbances²⁸. Clinical manifestations include frequent enuresis with a small amount of urine, constitutional pallor, fatigue, lack of appetite, loose stools, poor digestion, weak chronic cough, debilitated voice, spontaneous sweating, pale tongue, and slow pulse^{24,50}. Lung deficiency compromises its functions of dispersing and descending body fluids toward the Kidneys, impairing the passage of water and urinary control by the Bladder. Pulmonary debility interferes with the descending function of *Qi*, resulting in shortness of breath and weak cough. Furthermore, the disturbance in the mechanism of opening and closing the pores favours the occurrence of spontaneous nocturnal sweating⁵¹. In turn, as the Spleen governs the muscles, its deficiency generates an imbalance in muscle tone, including the tone of the muscles responsible for urination control. The functional debility of the Spleen compromises the transportation and transformation of fluids, which can facilitate involuntary urination, especially during sleep, when the body is in a state of relaxation. Additionally, Spleen dysfunction can lead to the accumulation of dampness in the Middle *Jiao*, manifesting through symptoms such as lack of appetite and loose stools. Lung and Spleen *Qi* deficiency also compromises the production of *Qi* and blood, as well as the capacity to transform and transport the essence of food throughout the organism. This dysfunction results in a pale constitution, fatigue, and general decrease in vitality. Due to *Qi* insufficiency, a reduction in blood supply is observed, which manifests clinically through signs such as pale tongue and slow or deep pulse²⁵.

Damp-Heat in the Liver Meridian

When Liver *Qi* stagnates, often due to emotional tension, diet, or infection, heat and dampness may accumulate in the Lower *Jiao*, disturbing Bladder function^{28,29,31}. Children with this pattern exhibit irritability, restless sleep, thirst, flushed face, and yellow, strong-smelling urine. The tongue often presents a yellow coating, and the pulse is rapid and

slippery^{24,50,52}. Treatment therefore focuses on clearing heat, resolving dampness, and regulating Liver *Qi*.

These patterns underline how TCM interprets CNE as a systemic imbalance rather than a localised urological dysfunction, emphasising individualised and holistic therapeutic strategies.

The Liver is responsible for ensuring the free circulation of *Qi* throughout the organism, and any interruption in this flow can cause imbalances in other organs. The syndrome in question has as its main aetiology the stagnation of Liver *Qi*, which may result from emotional factors, inadequate diet, or the invasion of wind-cold transforming into heat in the Liver meridian. Frequently, Liver *Qi* stagnation compromises emotional flow, just as emotional imbalances, especially anger and frustration, can negatively affect the energetic function of the Liver³¹. An inadequate diet interferes with the functioning of the Spleen, which begins to perform its functions ineffectively, compromising the metabolism of fluids and favouring the accumulation of dampness-heat, also in the Lower Jiao^{28,29,50,52}.

3.3. Traditional Chinese Therapeutic Approaches for Childhood Nocturnal Enuresis

Throughout TCM history, treatment approaches have evolved according to philosophical and clinical paradigms. The Han Dynasty emphasised warming and tonifying; the Song Dynasty focused on astringency and fluid conservation; and by the Ming Dynasty, syndrome differentiation became central^{53,54}.

Core treatment principles include warming and nourishing Kidney *Yang*, strengthening the Spleen and Lung, harmonising Liver *Qi*, eliminating dampness, and calming the Shen.

Therapeutic modalities applied in Chinese paediatrics include:

- Acupuncture: Activates the Bladder and Kidney meridians, regulating urination and calming the mind. The most frequently employed points include *Zhong Ji* (CV3), *Guan Yuan* (CV4), *Qi Hai* (CV6), *Shen Shu* (BL23), *Ci Liao* (BL32), *Tai Xi* (KI3), *Zu San Li* (ST36), *San Yin Jiao* (SP6), *Tai Chong* (LR3), *Qu Quan* (LR8), *Shen Men* (HT7), *Yin Tang* (EX-HN3), and *Bai Hui* (GV20)^{23,25,27,29,53}.
- Herbal medicine: Formulas such as *Jin Suo Gu Jing Wan*, *Jin Gui Shen Qi Wan*, *Suo Quan Wan*, and *Bu Zhong Yi Qi Wan*, *Zhi Bai Di Huang Wan*, *Long Dan Xie Gan Wan*; tonify Kidney and Spleen *Qi* while regulating bladder function^{25,26}.
- Cupping: Promote *Qi* circulation, eliminate cold, and strengthen *Yang*^{25,29}.
- Auriculotherapy: Stimulates auricular points like *Shen Men*, *Kidney*, *Bladder*, *Subcortex*, and *Tension* to balance *Qi* and regulate emotions^{25,29}.
- Dietary therapy: Uses specific foods and preparation, such as such as cooked rice and pork bladder with *Poria* (Chinese fungus) and lotus seeds is recommended, these having astringent and calming properties, in addition to recipes such as boiled egg with white pepper or chicken liver with cinnamon, indicated to warm and tonify *Yang*. However, caution is necessary due to the risk of irritation in young children²⁸.

Among these, paediatric *Tui Na* is especially valued for its safety, simplicity, and adaptability, making it ideal for children and suitable for integration with other therapies^{23,28,29,51,55,56}.

3.4. Principles and Mechanisms Tui Na

The term *Tui Na* comes from the words "Tui" (to push) and "Na" (to grasp), designating a therapeutic practice that, through body manipulation, promotes energetic and physiological reactions capable of restoring organic balance, strengthening the body.

In TCM, paediatric *Tui Na* is a branch of this technique, used since the Ming and Qing Dynasties in the treatment of various childhood illnesses, in addition to contributing to the strengthening of immunity, also acting in the prevention of common childhood diseases. Unlike the application in adults, paediatric *Tui Na* uses specific points and zones of

the child's body, characterised by lighter, gentler, and more harmonious manoeuvres, yet rapid, vigorous, and stimulating, without causing pain, with an average duration of 2 minutes or 70 to 300 repetitions per point or area ^{26,29,51}. The intensity of the manoeuvres varies according to the child's age and the treated region. This approach is considered highly effective and can be applied alone or in association with other therapies. It stands out for its good acceptance among children, as it is a non-invasive and comfortable technique ^{23,28,29,51,55,56}.

By stimulating acupoints and specific areas, *Tui Na* enhances the flow of *Qi* and *Xue*, clears meridian blockages, tonifies deficiencies, disperses pathogenic factors, and harmonises internal organs. In the context of CNE, it strengthens Kidney *Qi*, regulates Bladder function, harmonises the Lower *Jiao*, and calms emotional agitation that may accompany nocturnal urination ^{25,29,51,57}.

The main manipulative techniques include ^{25,26,28,29,51}:

- *Zhi Tui Fa* (pushing) – stimulate the circulation of *Qi* and *Xue*, unblock the meridians, and reduce pain.
- *An Fa* (pressing) - Its objective is to warm the meridians, calm the mind, favor the free circulation of the collaterals, and relieve pain.
- *Rou Fa* (Kneading or Massaging) – This manoeuvre aims to move *Qi*, activate the circulation of *Xue*, clear the meridians, and favour the unblocking of the organs.
- *Cuo Fa* (Rubbing and Rolling) - promote the regulation of *Qi*, harmonise *Xue*, and relax tendons.
- *Nie Fa* (Pinching the Spine) – It seeks to favor the balance between *Yin* and *Yang*, regulate the circulation of *Qi* and *Xue*, harmonise the internal organs, and tonify deficiencies.
- *Ji Fa* (Pinching and Squeezing).) – eliminates stagnation and heat;
- *Ca Fa* (Rubbing) - promotes warming, facilitating the circulation of *Qi* in the meridians, tonifying deficiency, and stimulating original *Yang*.
- *Qie Fa* or *Qia* (Marking) - It has a calming effect, contributing to the reduction of fear and mental agitation, opens passages, drains orifices, and alleviates convulsions and spasms.
- *Yun Fa* (revolving) – harmonises internal organs.

3.5. Therapeutic Points and Meridian Zones in Paediatric *Tui Na* for Childhood Nocturnal Enuresis

In the analysis of the selection of points used in paediatric *Tui Na* for the treatment of CNE ^{23,25,26,28,29,50-52,57-59}, a greater concentration was found in regions corresponding to the *Du Mai* / Governing Vessel (GV) channels, *Ren Mai* / Conception Vessel (CV), Bladder and Spleen meridians, in addition to areas and lines distributed on the hands, forearms, abdomen, and lumbosacral region. These elements are organised below according to their anatomical location (Table 1).

Basic Manipulations

Although there is no absolute consensus in the literature on the adoption of basic manipulations (Table 2) and additional manoeuvres (Table 3), selected according to the differential diagnosis of syndromes, there is a majority tendency among authors to adopt similar approaches as a therapeutic strategy in the treatment of CNE, although some present divergent approaches. All, however, have as a common objective to restore Kidney *Yang*, cultivate essence, tonify the Spleen, invigorate *Qi*, and harmonise the Liver ^{23,25,26,28,29,50-52,57-59}.

Table 1. Anatomical Location of paediatric *Tui na* Points.

Region	Point / Line	Meridian / Channel	Location / Description
Palm & Anterior Forearm	<i>Pi Jing</i>	Spleen	Distal Phalanx Of The Thumb
	<i>Shen Jing</i>	Kidney	Distal Phalanx Of The Fifth Finger
	<i>Gan Jing</i>	Liver	Distal Phalanx Of The Index Finger
	<i>Fei Jing</i>	Lung	Distal Phalanx Of The Fourth Finger
	<i>San Guan</i>	–	Anterior Forearm, Radial Side
	<i>Tian He Shui</i>	–	Anterior Forearm, Central Line
	<i>Liu Fu</i>	–	Anterior Forearm, Ulnar Side
Dorsum Of Hand & Posterior Forearm	<i>Wai Lao Gong</i>	–	Center Of Dorsum Of The Hand
	<i>Er Ma / Er Ren Shang Ma</i>	–	Depression Between 4th And 5th Mcp Joints
	<i>Bo Yang Chi</i>	–	3 <i>Cun</i> Above Center Of Wrist Extensor Crease
Abdomen	<i>Fu Yin Yang</i>	–	Line Below Costal Margins
	<i>Shen Que / Qi Zhong</i> (Cv8)	Conception Vessel	At The Navel
	<i>Qi Hai</i> (Cv6)	Conception Vessel	Anterior Midline, 1.5 <i>Cun</i> Below Navel
	<i>Dan Tian</i>	–	Pubic Region, Between Navel & Pubic Bone
	<i>Zhong Ji</i> (Cv3)	Conception Vessel	Anterior Midline, 4 <i>Cun</i> Below Navel
	<i>Qu Gu</i> (Cv2)	Conception Vessel	Upper Border Of Pubic Bone, Central
	Dorsal Region	<i>Ji Zhu</i>	–
<i>Fei Shu</i> (Bl13)		Bladder	1.5 <i>Cun</i> Lateral To T3 Spinous Process
<i>Xin Shu</i> (Bl15)		Bladder	1.5 <i>Cun</i> Lateral To T5 Spinous Process
<i>Gan Shu</i> (Bl18)		Bladder	1.5 <i>Cun</i> Lateral To T9 Spinous Process
<i>Pi Shu</i> (Bl20)		Bladder	1.5 <i>Cun</i> Lateral To T11 Spinous Process
<i>Wei Shu</i> (Bl21)		Bladder	1.5 <i>Cun</i> Lateral To T12 Spinous Process
<i>Shen Shu</i> (Bl23)		Bladder	1.5 <i>Cun</i> Lateral To L2 Spinous Process
<i>Ming Men</i> (GV4)		Governing Vessel	Posterior Midline, Below L2 Spinous Process
<i>Qi Jie Gu</i>		–	Line From Coccyx Tip To L4
<i>Pang Guang Shu</i> (Bl28)		Bladder	1.5 <i>Cun</i> Lateral To S2
<i>Ba Liao</i>		–	Sacrum, 4 Sacral Foramina Each Side
<i>Gui Wei</i> (GV1)		Governing Vessel	Lower End Of Coccyx
Lower Limbs		<i>Zu San Li</i> (St36)	Stomach
	<i>San Yin Jiao</i> (Sp6)	Spleen	Medial Leg, 3 <i>Cun</i> Above Medial Malleolus
	<i>Tai Chong</i> (LR3)	Liver	Dorsum Of Foot, Between 1st & 2nd Metatarsals
	<i>Yong Quan</i> (KI1)	Kidney	Depression On Sole, Anterior 1/3 To Middle 1/3
Head	<i>Bai Hui</i> (GV20)	Governing Vessel	Top Of Head, centre Line Connecting Ears

The clinical literature offers accumulating evidence that paediatric massage, often combined with adjunctive TCM techniques, may enhance therapeutic outcomes in childhood enuresis. For example, Lou⁵⁵ found that children receiving paediatric massage combined with moxibustion and acupoint application achieved improved rates of continence compared to standard care, indicating a synergistic effect of manual therapy plus heat and acupoint stimulation. Wang *et al.*⁵⁶ demonstrated that meridian-viscera massage combined with moxibustion in children with spleen- and Kidney-deficiency subtype of enuresis resulted in clinically meaningful improvements in nocturnal bed-wetting, thereby aligning treatment to TCM pattern differentiation. Su *et al.*⁶⁰ reported short- and long-term efficacy of massage in primary enuresis in children, noting sustained benefits and low relapse rates over follow-up. Yan⁶¹ focused on the renal-*Qi* deficiency subtype, applying *Tui Na* for “warming the Kidney and strengthening the spleen” and documented

favourable responses in enuretic children. Wang *et al.*⁶² used data-mining to analyse acupoint selection rules in massage treatments for paediatric enuresis, revealing consistent patterns in point usage (e.g., Kidney and Bladder meridian acupoints) that support protocol standardisation. Su *et al.*⁵⁹ reviewed the status of research on *Tui Na* for paediatric enuresis, highlighting methodological limitations (small sample sizes, short follow-up, heterogeneity) but nevertheless confirming clinical promise.

Table 2. Basic *Tui Na* Manipulations Used in the Treatment of paediatric Enuresis.

Point / Line	Meridian / Channel	Manipulation / Technique	Therapeutic Purpose
<i>Shen Jing</i>	Kidney	Slide With Tip Of Thumb Distal → Proximal	Tonify Kidney
<i>Pi Jing</i>	Spleen	Slide With Tip Of Thumb Distal → Proximal	Strengthen Spleen, Eliminate Dampness
<i>Wai Lao Gong</i>	–	Circular Pressing	Disperse Cold, Warm Lower <i>Jiao</i>
<i>San Guan</i>	–	Push With Index & Middle Fingers From Wrist To Elbow	Harmonise <i>Qi</i> , Strengthen <i>Yang</i> , Cultivate <i>Jing</i> , Disperse Bladder Cold
<i>Fu Yin Yang</i>	–	Slide With Thumbs From Center Outward	Strengthen Spleen
<i>Shen Que (Cv8)</i>	Conception Vessel	Circular Movements With Palm	Warm <i>Yang</i> , Strengthen Spleen, Tonify Deficiencies
<i>Dan Tian (Cv4)</i>	–	Circular Kneading With Palm Base	Tonify Kidney, Tonify Lower <i>Jiao</i>
<i>Zhong Ji (Cv3)</i>	Conception Vessel	Kneading	Strengthen Kidney, Nourish Essence
<i>Qu Gu (Cv2)</i>	Conception Vessel	Press & Rotate	Tonify Kidney, Tonify Lower <i>Jiao</i>
<i>Shen Shu (Bl23)</i>	Bladder	Circular Movements On Dorsal Shu	Tonify Kidney & <i>Jing</i>
<i>Pang Guang Shu (Bl28)</i>	Bladder	Circular Movements On Dorsal Shu	Strengthen Bladder Function
<i>Ming Men (GV4)</i>	Governing Vessel	Rub Palms & Place Over Point	Warm Region, Tonify Original <i>Qi</i> , Strengthen Kidney <i>Yang</i>
<i>Qi Jie Gu</i>	–	Push Upward	Tonify Deficiencies
<i>Gui Wei (GV1)</i>	Governing Vessel	Circular Kneading	Warm <i>Yang</i> , Calm Fear
<i>Ji Zhu</i>	–	Pinch & Roll Along Spine; Bottom → Top (Deficiency), Top → Bottom (Excess)	Harmonise <i>Zang-Fu</i> , Regulate <i>Yin-Yang</i> , Regulate <i>Qi</i> & <i>Xue</i>
<i>San Yin Jiao (Sp6)</i>	Spleen	Press & Rotate	Strengthen Liver, Kidney, Spleen; Disperse Dampness-Heat; Regulate Lower Burner
<i>Zu San Li (St36)</i>	Stomach	Press	Regulate & Strengthen <i>Qi</i> Of Middle Burner, Increase <i>Yang</i> , Eliminate Dampness/Cold, Strengthen Body & Immunity
<i>Bai Hui (GV20)</i>	Governing Vessel	Circular Pressing	Tonify <i>Jing</i> , Calm Mind, Soothe Fear

The clinical literature offers accumulating evidence that paediatric massage, often combined with adjunctive TCM techniques, may enhance therapeutic outcomes in childhood enuresis. For example, Lou⁵⁵ found that children receiving paediatric massage combined with moxibustion and acupoint application achieved improved rates of continence compared to standard care, indicating a synergistic effect of manual therapy plus heat and

acupoint stimulation. Wang *et al.*⁵⁶ demonstrated that meridian-viscera massage combined with moxibustion in children with spleen- and Kidney-deficiency subtype of enuresis resulted in clinically meaningful improvements in nocturnal bed-wetting, thereby aligning treatment to TCM pattern differentiation. Su *et al.*⁶⁰ reported short- and long-term efficacy of massage in primary enuresis in children, noting sustained benefits and low relapse rates over follow-up. Yan⁶¹ focused on the renal-*Qi* deficiency subtype, applying *Tui Na* for “warming the Kidney and strengthening the spleen” and documented favourable responses in enuretic children. Wang *et al.*⁶² used data-mining to analyse acupoint selection rules in massage treatments for paediatric enuresis, revealing consistent patterns in point usage (e.g., Kidney and Bladder meridian acupoints) that support protocol standardisation. Su *et al.*⁵⁹ reviewed the status of research on *Tui Na* for paediatric enuresis, highlighting methodological limitations (small sample sizes, short follow-up, heterogeneity) but nevertheless confirming clinical promise.

Table 3. Additional paediatric Tuina Manipulations According to Syndrome Differentiation.

Syndrome / Pattern	Point / Line	Meridian / Channel	Manipulation / Technique	Therapeutic Purpose
Kidney <i>Qi</i> Insufficiency	<i>Er Ma</i> (Two Horses)	–	Circular Pressing	Recover <i>Yang</i> , Promote <i>Qi</i> Circulation, Tonify Kidney
	<i>Ba Liao</i> (Eight Sacral Orifices)	–	Rub With Palm Until Warm	Tonify, Warm, Consolidate Lower <i>Jiao</i>
	<i>Yong Quan</i> (KI1)	Kidney	Press	Tonify <i>Qi</i> & Essence, Restore Energetic Balance
Spleen and Lung <i>Qi</i> Deficiency	<i>Fei Jing Line</i>	Lung	Slide With Thumb Distal → Proximal	Strengthen Lung Function
	<i>Fei Shu</i> (BL13)	Bladder	Circular Pressing	Tonify Lung <i>Qi</i>
	<i>Xin Shu</i> (BL15)	Bladder	Circular Pressing	Regulate Heart <i>Qi</i>
	<i>Pi Shu</i> (BL20)	Bladder	Circular Pressing	Tonify Spleen, Disperse Dampness
	<i>Wei Shu</i> (BL21)	Bladder	Circular Pressing	Tonify Stomach
Dampness-Heat in Liver Meridian	<i>Gan Jing Line</i>	Liver	Slide Thumb Proximal → Distal	Harmonise Liver, Eliminate Heat, Calm Fear
	<i>Liu Fu Line</i>	–	Push With Index & Middle Fingers Elbow → Wrist	Favours Viscera Function, Cool Heat
	<i>Tian He Shui Line</i>	–	Slide Wrist → Elbow	Eliminate Heat, Dissipate Dampness, Calm Mind & Fear
	<i>Bo Yang Chi</i>	–	Circular Pressing	Disperse Heat
	<i>Yong Quan</i> (KI1)	Kidney	Press	Eliminate Heat, Decrease Irritability
	<i>Tai Chong</i> (LR3)	Liver	Press	Subdue Liver <i>Yang</i> , Move <i>Qi</i> , Eliminate Dampness
	<i>Si Heng Wen</i> (Four Transverse Creases)	–	Push, Pinch, Knead Palmar Mcp Joints 2nd–5th Fingers	Effective For Dampness-Heat Liver Type

Together, these studies corroborate the meta-analytical findings that *Tui Na* is a promising adjunctive therapy for childhood nocturnal enuresis²³ by showing: (1) integration with moxibustion and acupoint application appears to enhance efficacy^{55,56}, (2) pattern-based protocol design (renal-*Qi* deficiency, Spleen-Kidney *Yang* deficiency) improves alignment with TCM theory and likely outcomes^{61,62}, and (3) manual massage interventions may deliver sustained benefits over time⁵⁹. However, persistent limitations remain: many of the studies are not randomised controlled trials, sample sizes are modest, follow-up durations are short, and there is frequent lack of objective mechanistic data or blinding, issues also flagged by the systematic review²³.

4. Final Remarks and Conclusions

CNE remains a common paediatric condition with complex, multifactorial origins that encompass physiological, emotional, and developmental factors. Beyond its physical manifestations, the disorder significantly impacts a child's self-esteem, confidence, and family relationships. Conventional medicine provides behavioural and pharmacological strategies with variable outcomes and frequent relapse after treatment cessation. Consequently, integrative approaches that consider both physiological and psychosocial dimensions have gained increasing importance.

Within TCM, paediatric *Tui Na* emerges as a particularly valuable therapeutic tool. Based on the principles of energetic balance, it regulates the flow of *Qi* and *Xue*, strengthens the Kidney, Spleen, and Bladder functions, and harmonises *Yin* and *Yang*. The evidence summarised in this narrative review demonstrates that paediatric *Tui Na* effectively reduces the frequency of enuretic episodes, improves bladder control, enhances sleep quality, and contributes to emotional stability and self-esteem in children.

Furthermore, *Tui Na* offers practical advantages: it is non-invasive, well accepted by children, and can be taught to parents or caregivers, allowing continuity of treatment at home. This participatory approach strengthens the emotional bond between caregiver and child, promoting comfort, trust, and therapeutic adherence, elements crucial for successful outcomes.

Despite its longstanding tradition and encouraging clinical evidence, paediatric *Tui Na* remains underexplored in Western medicine. The current scarcity of large-scale, methodologically rigorous clinical trials highlights the need for further research to substantiate its mechanisms of action and optimise treatment protocols. Future studies should aim to integrate traditional diagnostic frameworks with modern evidence-based methodologies, ensuring broader acceptance and applicability within paediatric healthcare systems.

In conclusion, paediatric *Tui Na* represents a promising, safe, and effective integrative therapy for childhood nocturnal enuresis, addressing both physiological and emotional dimensions of the disorder. It exemplifies the potential of traditional therapies to complement contemporary paediatric medicine, fostering a holistic, patient-centred model of care.

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